

Cognitive infiltration and Dissidents' dissent

Peter Ayolov, Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski", 2022

(Ideas from the book *The Economic Policy of Online Media: Manufacture of Dissent*,
Routledge, 2024)

Abstract

This article analyses Cass R. Sunstein's contribution to contemporary theories of consent, dissent and social control in liberal democracies, with particular attention to his notions of 'libertarian paternalism' and 'cognitive infiltration'. It argues that Sunstein offers one of the clearest formulations of a 'manufacture of dissent' model adapted to digital mass communication. First, the article situates Sunstein's work within the longer tradition of democratic propaganda, from Lippmann, Lasswell and Bernays to the contemporary regulatory state. It examines his defence of dissent as a necessary condition of social capital and epistemic correction, as developed in *Why Societies Need Dissent* and *Republic.com 2.0*, and his attempt to reconcile free choice with guided decision-making through 'choice architecture' and 'soft paternalism' in *Nudge*. Second, the article turns to Sunstein and Vermeule's proposal for 'cognitive infiltration' of extremist and conspiratorial groups as a response to online conspiracy theories that undermine trust in democratic institutions. It reconstructs their argument for active state intervention in the informational environment and contrasts it with critical reactions from journalists and dissident scholars, who interpret such strategies as extensions of earlier programmes of covert surveillance and disruption. The conclusion contends that while Sunstein seeks to preserve democracy by managing dissent, the systematic manufacture and manipulation of dissent risks eroding social capital, deepening mistrust and transforming genuine dissidents into objects of administrative control.

Keywords: Cass Sunstein; dissent; libertarian paternalism; cognitive infiltration; conspiracy theories; manufacture of dissent; social capital; propaganda; digital democracy

Cass R. Sunstein's work on consent and dissent in liberal democracies marks a decisive shift in the theory of mass communication from the exclusive focus on 'manufacturing consent' to a more complex equilibrium in which dissent is not only tolerated but strategically produced and managed. For Sunstein, both consent and dissent are crucial indicators of democratic vitality and of the level of social capital in a polity. The task of government is not merely to secure obedience, but to regulate the balance between agreement and disagreement in order to maintain confidence in democratic principles and institutions. This places him squarely within the tradition of authors such as Walter Lippmann, Harold Lasswell and Edward Bernays, who justified forms of democratic propaganda, but it also pushes that tradition into the specific conditions of the internet age. Sunstein's public influence during the Obama administration underscores the practical relevance of his theories. As head of the White House Office of Information and Regulatory Affairs (2009–2012), sometimes labelled the 'Information Czar', and co-author of the report *Liberty and Security in a Changing World*, he helped articulate a framework for regulating information flows in a digitally networked society. In that context he

proposed institutional mechanisms, such as a Bureau of Internet and Cyberspace Affairs, to manage information deemed dangerous to national stability. His concern is that limitless individual choice in an environment of unlimited information can produce outcomes that are harmful both to citizens and to the democratic system: people may come to desire changes to the information order and even to the state itself. In *Republic.com 2.0* Sunstein warns of 'information cocoons' and 'echo chambers' created by technologies that allow citizens to filter their informational environment so that they encounter only like-minded voices. The question he poses is what becomes of democracy and free speech when the internet's promise of unlimited choice is used to avoid exposure to disagreement. The answer he proposes is not a return to a top-down propaganda model aimed solely at manufacturing consent, but a reconfigured model in which controlled doses of dissent are deliberately fostered and channelled.

This logic is articulated more systematically in Sunstein's concept of 'libertarian paternalism', presented with Richard H. Thaler in *Nudge: Improving Decisions about Health, Wealth, and Happiness*. The core claim is that individuals' behaviour is often governed by 'bounded rationality', cognitive biases and irrational motives. Because of this, people sometimes make choices that are contrary to their own long-term interests. Libertarian paternalism proposes that public and private institutions can design 'choice architectures' that gently 'nudge' individuals towards better decisions, while formally preserving freedom of choice. In this view, a fatherly push, calibrated to respect autonomy, is justified in the name of social progress and individual welfare. Transposed into the domain of mass communication, this approach represents a continuation of the paternalism of the educated elite, but in a softer, less coercive form. Whereas the classical propaganda model relied on strong filters and one-way media systems, Sunstein openly acknowledges the need for dissent in a free society and recognises its positive contribution to social capital. However, dissent is primarily conceived as a speech act within a managed environment, rather than as a basis for genuine collective action. It is to be encouraged and, where necessary, constructed so that it can serve as a safety valve and a source of information for policymakers, without endangering the underlying order.

In *Why Societies Need Dissent* Sunstein develops a normative defence of disagreement as a moral obligation, particularly for intellectuals and members of epistemic elites. Silence in times of moral crisis, he argues, is typically a group phenomenon; individuals who break with group opinion and express dissent perform a vital corrective function. Historical and experimental evidence, including the work of Stanley Milgram on obedience and Solomon Asch on conformity, shows that people are strongly inclined to follow authority and the majority, even when they privately doubt the correctness of commands or judgments. For that reason, societies require dissidents who resist pressures to conform, present alternative perspectives and thus expand the range of options available to the community. Technological developments magnify this dynamic. The nineteenth-century expansion of the cheap press contributed to the revolutionary 'Spring of the Nations'; in parallel, the spread of social networks and low-cost online publishing has enabled movements such as the Arab Spring. In both cases, lowering the barriers to publication increased the visibility of conflicting viewpoints and grievances, raising the overall level of dissent. For Sunstein, this capacity to break 'the silence' of encapsulated groups and to disrupt group isolation is a central democratic good: without exposure to differing opinions, people are more likely to succumb to conformism and polarisation. At the same time, Sunstein insists on the symbolic and practical importance of law and institutions. In his view, the moral authority of law typically exceeds that of fluctuating public opinion; citizens obey

legal norms not only out of fear but because they believe in their general fairness and endurance. Democracies can therefore elicit consent without overt coercion, as long as citizens trust that the legal system and mass media broadly reflect their interests. Under these conditions, propaganda is not an alien imposition but a technique of persuasion that operates within an accepted framework of legitimacy.

Sunstein's distinctive—and controversial—move is to combine this defence of dissent and free speech with an explicit endorsement of the state's right to manipulate public opinion for the public good. If freedom of speech is guaranteed, he contends, then freedom of propaganda and even of certain forms of manipulation follows as a corollary: the state may not censor speech, but it can legitimately attempt to influence the informational environment through strategic communication. The unresolved question is when, if ever, the risks posed by particular forms of speech are sufficiently great to justify restrictions. It is precisely this question that Sunstein and Adrian Vermeule address in their 2008 article 'Conspiracy Theories'. Confronted with the proliferation of online narratives that deny official accounts of events such as the 9/11 attacks, and that portray the state as a malevolent conspirator, they argue that such theories threaten trust in democratic institutions and can generate serious risks. In response, they propose a range of measures, from counterspeech and public education to more interventionist strategies, including what they call 'cognitive infiltration' of extremist groups. Cognitive infiltration entails the deployment of government agents or allied actors, operating openly or anonymously, in physical or virtual spaces, to insert doubts into the 'crippled epistemologies' of conspiratorial communities. These agents would provide alternative information, contest key 'stylised facts' and introduce greater cognitive diversity, thereby weakening the internal coherence of such groups. Sunstein and Vermeule also canvas the possibility of legal sanctions, discrediting campaigns and the strategic employment of counter-narratives. In extreme cases, they even suggest that censorship may be warranted, despite its tension with traditional liberal principles.

The logic of cognitive infiltration represents a fully articulated 'manufacture of dissent' model. Rather than simply suppressing unwanted opinions, it seeks to multiply and manage them: to drown 'dangerous' dissent in a sea of controlled, less threatening disagreements and spurious conspiracies. In such a system, the dissent of genuine dissidents circulates alongside, and is often overshadowed by, manufactured controversies and diversionary narratives. The result is that dissent functions as a safety valve and an intelligence source, while its capacity to destabilise the status quo is reduced. This proposal has attracted sharp criticism from journalists and independent scholars. Glenn Greenwald, for example, described Sunstein's recommendations as a 'spine-chilling' blueprint for state penetration of anti-government groups, noting the parallels with earlier covert operations. David Ray Griffin and Michel Chossudovsky interpret cognitive infiltration as part of a broader strategy whereby corporate and state elites encourage limited, controllable forms of opposition in order to preserve the illusion of democracy. For Chossudovsky, contemporary capitalism no longer seeks to eliminate dissent, but to stage and fund it as a managed spectacle that dissipates social energy without enabling structural change. Historical precedents such as COINTELPRO, the FBI's programme of surveillance, infiltration and disruption of domestic political organisations between 1956 and 1971, lend weight to these concerns. Even when justified in the name of national security or social stability, such operations often targeted legitimate movements for civil rights, peace and gender equality. Applied to the digital environment, cognitive infiltration risks reproducing these patterns on a larger scale, with potentially profound consequences for

social capital. Trust, once eroded by systematic deception and manipulation, is slow and difficult to rebuild.

Conclusion: Dissidents' Dissent and the Limits of Managed Pluralism

The trajectory of Sunstein's work illustrates a deep ambivalence at the heart of contemporary democratic theory. On the one hand, he offers a robust defence of dissent as an epistemic and moral necessity: societies need dissidents to challenge groupthink, expose errors and expand the range of possible futures. On the other hand, he assigns to the state and allied institutions an extensive mandate to design informational environments, nudge preferences and infiltrate oppositional groups in order to contain what is perceived as dangerous or destabilising dissent. This double movement effectively transforms dissent from an autonomous practice rooted in conscience and social experience into a variable to be managed within a technocratic apparatus. Libertarian paternalism and cognitive infiltration are both expressions of a broader shift from the manufacture of consent to the strategic manufacture and modulation of dissent. In such a system, the dissent of dissidents is simultaneously valued and neutralised: it is encouraged insofar as it enriches public debate and legitimises the democratic order, yet monitored and fragmented so that it does not crystallise into effective challenges to power. The long-term implications for social capital are troubling. Trust depends on the belief that communication is, at least in part, sincere and that institutions are bound by norms of transparency and accountability. When citizens come to suspect that both consent and dissent are being systematically engineered—through choice architectures, propaganda campaigns or covert infiltration—the basic conditions for trust are undermined. Even if such strategies yield short-term stability, they risk deepening cynicism, apathy and polarisation over time. The analysis suggests that dissidents' dissent cannot be sustainably manufactured from above without damaging the very democratic fabric it is supposed to protect. Genuine dissent arises from lived experience, moral conviction and spontaneous association, not from administrative design. A democracy that relies too heavily on informational management and cognitive engineering may preserve its formal procedures, but it becomes increasingly 'decorative': outwardly pluralist, inwardly governed by techniques of control. If pluralism and openness are indeed prerequisites for progress, as Sunstein himself argues, then the task is not to infiltrate and fragment dissent, but to create conditions in which independent voices can emerge, be heard and contest power without fear of manipulation. That requires limits on the instrumental use of communication by states and corporations, and a renewed emphasis on the informal, trust-based foundations of social capital. Only under such conditions can dissent function as a genuine resource for democratic renewal, rather than as a managed component of a sophisticated system of social control.

Bibliography:

Chossudovsky, M. (2010). "Manufacturing Dissent": The Anti-globalization Movement is Funded by the Corporate Elites.' Global Research, 20 September 2010. Available at: <http://www.globalresearch.ca/manufacturing-dissent-the-anti-globalization-movement-is-funded-by-the-corporate-elites/21110> (Last visited 16.06.2020).

Griffin, D. R. (2011). *Cognitive Infiltration: An Obama Appointee's Plan to Undermine the 9/11 Conspiracy Theory*. Northampton, MA: Interlink Books.

Greenwald, G. (2010). 'Obama confidant's spine-chilling proposal: Cass Sunstein wants the government to "cognitively infiltrate" anti-government groups.' *Salon*, 15 January 2010. Available at: [\[www.salon.com/2010/01/15/sunstein_2/\]](http://www.salon.com/2010/01/15/sunstein_2/)(http://www.salon.com/2010/01/15/sunstein_2/) (Last visited 16.06.2020).

The United States President's Review Group on Intelligence and Communications Technologies. (2013). *Liberty and Security in a Changing World: Report and Recommendations of the President's Review Group on Intelligence and Communications Technologies*. Office of the Director of National Intelligence.

Sunstein, C. R. (2005). *Why Societies Need Dissent*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Sunstein, C. R. (2009). *Republic.com 2.0*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.

Sunstein, C. R. (2017). *#Republic: Divided Democracy in the Age of Social Media*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.

Sunstein, C. R., & Vermeule, A. (2008). 'Conspiracy Theories.' Harvard Public Law Working Paper.

Thaler, R. H., & Sunstein, C. R. (2008). *Nudge: Improving Decisions about Health, Wealth, and Happiness*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.